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Opportunities and Challenges of Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tools in English Language

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the opportunities and challenges of using Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in English language among college students enrolled in selected sectarian and non-sectarian Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Iloilo City, Philippines, during the first semester of School Year 2025–2026. Guided by a descriptive-correlational research design, the investigation utilized a validated researcher-made survey questionnaire administered to a stratified random sample of students. Data were analyzed through descriptive statistics to summarize student profiles and perceptions, while inferential statistics, including t-test, ANOVA, and Pearson r, were employed to determine group differences and relationships. Findings revealed that students generally perceived AI tools as highly beneficial for enhancing their writing proficiency, grammar, vocabulary, and academic productivity. Nevertheless, they also identified challenges such as limited originality, ethical concerns, over-reliance on AI outputs, and technical constraints. Results further indicated that while opportunities were recognized consistently across groups, challenges varied according to demographic and institutional factors. Moreover, opportunities and challenges were found to exist independently, with students acknowledging the advantages of AI tools while remaining aware of their limitations. The study concluded that AI holds substantial promise for English language learning, provided that its integration is guided by responsible and ethical use.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, English Language, Opportunities, Challenges, College Students

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